

How Social Thermodynamics could help Greece?

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Nevertheless people believe that they are not simply physical objects, one can try to approximate roughly the social dynamics by the use of the most general laws of thermodynamics. The basic equation, unifying the principles of thermodynamics, reads

$$dU \leq TdS - pdV + \mu dn \quad (1)$$

One can interpret now U as the social energy, T as the social temperature, S as the social entropy, p as the social pressure, V as the country volume, n as the number of people in the country and μ as the exploitation by society. It follows from Eq. (1) that the social entropy rises in an isolated country. Thus one can identify S with the social freedom as well, since higher disorder corresponds to larger number of degrees of freedom. Therefore, the social striving for Liberty is in fact a manifestation of the Second Law.

The basic results from thermodynamics can explain some empirical facts in societies. Thus in 'chemical' equilibrium, the exploitation μ is the same in all countries, while at non-equilibrium people migrate to countries with lower exploitation, e.g. from Bulgaria and Rumania to UK. Since at present no essential outflow of people from Greece is evident, one can conclude that Greece is still in 'chemical' equilibrium with Europe. According to thermodynamics the heat flows from a hotter to a cooler body. In analogy the hot democratic countries spread freedom in the surrounding and increase their social temperature, e.g. from USA to USSR in the early 90's. Any country possesses an equation of state, relating the social parameters, and revolutions are social phase transitions. It is a pity that no one knows the equation of state of Greece now. Note that according to non-equilibrium thermodynamics, the production of social entropy possesses a minimum at a stationary state, which explains the conservative behavior of the societies.

The 'mechanical' equilibrium requires equality of the social pressure in all countries. Its violation is the reason for wars between countries, accompanied by expansion and contraction. If the Greek people say "No" at the referendum today, the euro money flow will stop, which corresponds to $dU = 0$. Since the Greek people do not still migrate and $dn = 0$, Eq. (1) simplifies to $TdS \geq pdV$. There is no doubt about the economic contraction of Greece corresponding to a negative country volume change $dV < 0$. Hence, a stable state in Greece could be reached by a negative entropy production $dS < 0$ only. Therefore, one would expect freedom and democracy restrictions, imposed by a military regime, for instance. If the Greek people say "Yes" at the referendum, the money stream from Europe $dU > 0$ will cool the social temperature and decrease the social pressure but it is not clear for how long it will last until the Greek economy will start to generate surplus.